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A Novel Data Processing Technique for Expert Resonant Nano-Pillars Transducers: A Case Study Measuring Ethanol in Water and Wine Liquid Matrices

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ABSTRACT This paper proposes a novel readout methodology for improving the performance of Refractive Index (RI) based photonic transducers. Specifically, the authors focus on an optical transducer reported recently in the literature, the so-called Resonant Nano-Pillars (RNPs) transducer. The readout signal for this transducer is usually obtained based on the Wavelength Shift of the Resonant Mode (WSRM), which identifies a single point from the signal, such as the minimum of a resonant mode, whose wavelength shift or intensity value has a correlation with the RI of the media, and, therefore, with the monitored chemical component. This work proposes a novel spectral analysis through Principal Component Analysis (PCA), later inferring the property of interest by regression techniques. To evaluate the performance of the proposal, the authors mimic an agro-food experiment emulating a fermentation process as a proof of concept by measuring the ethanol concentration over time in two liquids: Deionized Water (DIW) and White Wine (WW). The authors compare both methods by inferring the ethanol concentration in the two experiments. As a result, the authors demonstrated experimentally that the proposal significantly outperformed the WSRM method, reporting an improvement of the Limit of Detection (LoD) of up to 140 times. Moreover, this PCA method can be also applied to many other biochemical sensing systems and transducers.

INDEX TERMS Chemical and biological sensors, optical sensors, optical resonators, machine learning, principal component analysis, expert sensors, resonant nano-pillars, chemical monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the industry is evolving towards the digital age to increase its efficiency and productivity, leading to the development of Industry 4.0 [1]. This advanced industrial approach allows an increment of the digital data with which to cre-

ate enhanced plant models [2]. For this reason, traditional monitoring systems are evolving towards distributed systems supported by the Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm [1], [3].

Attending to a relevant field as the agro-food industry, this innovative trend was successfully applied when exploring novel approaches for monitoring fluid properties [4], [5]. Focusing on this field of knowledge, there are two usual approaches of fluid characterization for a sample in the

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industry: i) getting its physicochemical properties (e.g., viscosity and density) and ii) its chemical composition. The physicochemical properties are generally provided with precision by industrial sensors in the production stage. However, it is challenging to obtain the chemical composition in a precise manner in the same production stage. Chemical composition analysis usually requires complex expensive equipment and trained personnel, which lead to performing such analysis in specialized laboratories, hindering real-world applications where the chemical composition of a sample should be provided almost instantaneously. Some examples in applying such complex equipment for chemical composition in the agro-food industry are in [6]–[9], where the authors considered UltraViolet (UV), Near-Infrared (NIR), and Mid-Infrared (MIR) optical transducers. As expected, such conventional transducers using complex equipment are not economically affordable in real-world applications for the agro-food domain.

As an alternative to this expensive laboratory oriented technology, optical sensing systems based on micro-nano structures are gaining popularity because of its reduced cost, response time, size, and high usability. Some examples of these alternative sensors are Fabry-Perot, Young and Mach-Zehnder interferometers, Surface Plasmon, and Ring Resonators [10]. As expected, this alternative technology has a limited performance compared to the traditional one, and then it is susceptible to improvement.

A recent alternative optical sensing system based on nano-structures was reported in [11]–[14], the Resonant Nano-Pillars (RNPs) transducers. The authors exposed that RNPs transducers can measure changes in the Refractive Index (RI) of fluids, using these changes to infer fluid properties, such as the density of the media or the concentration of a certain bio-molecule in biological fluids. Some reported advantages of RNPs transducers are related to increasing the quality factor of the optical response, producing a highly precise defined shape of the resonant mode, and a light confinement effect enhancing the sensing capacity [15].

The general response of an RNPs transducer consists of a resonant mode centered in a photonic band gap, e.g., the visible range. Figure 1 shows some RNPs transducer responses for several solvents measured with the same optical interrogation system considered in this work. In these spectra, it can be observed that not only the dip of the resonant mode is changing, but also the photonic band gap.

The readout signal for an RNPs response is usually obtained based on the Wavelength Shift Resonant Mode (WSRM), being the widely reported framework for generating the mathematical model to quantify a fluid property for RNPs transducers. The methodology for applying the WSRM method is as follows [11]–[14]: the RNPs response is reduced to a single point manually based on expertise. This point usually corresponds to the minimum point in the resonant mode valley, which has a correlation with the RI of the media among the pillars. Next, a linear regression model is built to infer a fluid property according to the wavelength shift (the

FIGURE 1. RNPs transducer responses for several solvents.

value of the point). It is worth to mention that the intensity of the signal, instead of the wavelength shift, can also be considered as an alternative.

Although the WSRM approach provides satisfactory performance, there are some open questions related to the loss of information by simplifying the signal to a single point of the whole spectral response, which could incur in a loss of performance. For instance, the loss can be generated because not only the resonant mode shifts when there is a change in the fluid properties, but the photonic band gap can also be moved, as Figure 1 shows.

An alternative method to the WSRM approach could be given by applying dimensionality reduction techniques from the Machine Learning (ML) field to the input signals. Reviewing the spectroscopy domain literature, this type of techniques was successfully applied to transform high-dimensional problems (with many variables) into low-dimensional ones (with a reduced number of variables) while maintaining a high percentage of the data variance explained [16]–[19]. A known dimensionality reduction technique in the spectroscopy field, mainly applied in NIR and MIR analysis [6], [7], [20], is the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [8], [21], [22]. PCA applies an orthogonal transformation to convert a set of observations of correlated variables into a set of linearly uncorrelated ones called Principal Components (PCs). Other successful cases in the use of PCA include drug discrimination [9], melamine detection in milk [23], identification of tea species [24], and flavor wine inference [25], among many others. The differences among these works and our proposal will be described below.

On this basis, this paper proposes a novel spectral sensing response analysis method in fluid characterization for improving the performance of photonic transducers, in this case focusing on RNPs transducers. This methodology is called PCA-based spectral analysis method by the authors. To this end, the authors combine the usage of PCA and regression learning methods. The proposal is successfully applied by mimicking an agro-food experiment, where ethanol concentration is predicted in both White Wine (WW) and DeIonized Water (DIW) liquid matrices. As a result of the proposal, the authors concluded experimentally that the sensing performance of RNPs transducers is improved

FIGURE 2. Flow chart for the data processing techniques applied in this work.

when comparing the PCA-based method to the WSRM approach. Note that the proposal here differs from the works discussed before ([9], [23]–[25]) applying PCA in that i) the problem addressed is of type regression, where the purpose is inferring the property of a sample in a continuous domain and ii) the origin of the data is different, coming from the RNP's transducers.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II describes the method proposed in this paper. Section III exposes the experimental methodology followed to test the proposal. Section IV discusses the experimental results by including a comparison between the PCA-based spectral analysis method proposed and the WSRM approach. Section V concludes the paper with some final remarks.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

This section describes the PCA-based spectral analysis method proposed, which is composed of two stages: dimensionality reduction and inference. As stated before, the signal obtained from the RNP's transducer is a multivariate response, forming the attribute space. The first stage of the PCA-based approach is to transform the many-attribute space into a reduced one with fewer variables while maintaining a high percentage of the data variance explained. The second stage infers the property of interest in the experiment according to the reduced attribute space. Note that both stages follow a data-driven approach and then, a dataset is needed to develop the model inside [26].

For a better understanding of the reader, Figure 2 shows a flow chart comparing the proposal to the WSRM method. In this figure, both methods include a stage for reducing the RNP's response, which is followed by an inference stage, predicting the property of interest for the system.

A. FIRST STAGE: DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION

This stage reduces an RNP's signal through PCA. To this end, the coefficients of PCA should be found through a training stage according to a set of representative RNP's responses. On this basis, this section first formally describes the training stage of PCA for the use case and next, it describes how to

get a reduced RNP's signal based on the coefficients of PCA. Let X be the signal matrix saving the RNP's responses used to train PCA, with $X \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, where m is the number of RNP's responses and n is the number of points in a response. Then, four sets of data should be generated before getting the trained PCA model, these are:

- The signal mean vector \bar{X} contains the average value of each point in X , that is

$$\bar{X} = [\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_n]^T, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{x}_j \in \bar{X}$ is the mean value of the j -th point in the signal for the m signals, with $j \in 1, \dots, n$.

- The covariance matrix Σ contains the variances and covariances of the points of the signals in X , that is

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{n-1}(X - \bar{X})(X - \bar{X}). \quad (2)$$

- The eigenvalue vector Λ , which is calculated based on Σ , contains the variance of each PC, that is

$$\Lambda = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n]^T, \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda_j \in \Lambda$ is the variance of the j -th PC in the projection space.

- The eigenvector matrix W , which is calculated based on Σ , contains the coefficients for inferring future PCA projections, *i.e.*, the reduced RNP's signals, that is

$$W = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n]^T, \quad (4)$$

where $w_j \in W$ is the eigenvector of the j -th PC. Information about eigenvector calculation is in [27].

The number of PCs needed to represent the response of the RNP's transducer in a low-dimensional space can be calculated using the cumulative percentage variance approach in Algorithm 1 [28]–[30]. This algorithm starts sorting Λ and W in descending order, resulting in Λ' and W' , so that PCs are placed from higher to lower explained variance (see line 1). Then, the cumulative percentage variance denoted as cvp is calculated as

$$cvp = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^z \lambda'_k}{\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda'_j} 100, \quad (5)$$

where $\lambda'_k \in \Lambda'$ is the variance of the k -th PC in the sorted vector and z is the number of PCs, which is increased over iterations until cpv takes a value higher than a given threshold CPV_{th} , usually equaling 95% (see lines 2-5 in Algorithm 1).

Algorithm 1 Cumulative Percentage Variance Algorithm

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 $\Lambda' \leftarrow \text{sort}(\Lambda)$ ,  $W' \leftarrow \text{sort}(W)$ ,  $z \leftarrow 0$ ,  $cpv \leftarrow 0$ 
while  $cpv \leq CPV_{th}$  do
   $z \leftarrow z + 1$ 
   $cpv \leftarrow \sum_{k=1}^z \lambda'_k / \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda'_j$ 
end while=0
  
```

As a result of Algorithm 1, z saves the number of PCs used to represent the RNPs response in a low-dimensional space, with $z \ll n$. Consequently, we should define an additional eigenvector matrix W'' with fewer PCs than W' , that is

$$W'' = [w'_1, w'_2, \dots, w'_z]^T, \quad (6)$$

where w'_k is the n -dimensional eigenvector of the k -th PC in the sorted vector W' . Note that W'' has a fewer number of columns than W' , but the same number of rows.

Once PCA training is performed, it is possible to represent an RNPs response in a low-dimensional space as given by

$$Y = W''(S - \bar{X}), \quad (7)$$

where S is a set of RNPs responses to simplify and Y is the set of resulting projections of S in the space defined by PCA with z dimensions.

B. SECOND STAGE: INFERENCE

This stage infers a property of the compound from the reduced RNP signal obtained according to equation (7). To this end, we should first select a regression learning method from ML to infer the property of interest based on the reduced RNP signals. As before, the coefficients of the regression learning method should be found through a training stage according to a set of representative RNP reduced responses, which should be adequately labeled because of the supervised strategy. An example of how to select the training samples and the regression algorithm will be shown during the experimental evaluation in Section IV.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

As introduced before, the benefits of the proposal are analyzed in a real agro-food experiment. Thus, this section first describes the RNPs transducers considered. Second, it details the optical interrogation system employed for getting the experimental data. Third, it is described how the two experiments are performed. Finally, performance metrics are introduced to later analyze the data obtained in Section IV.

A. RNPS TRANSDUCERS

An RNPs transducer is composed of a periodic array of nano-pillars transducers made of Bragg Reflectors with a central resonant nano-cavity in the middle. A single RNP is acting as a nano-sensor and the array of multiple RNPs is

what is considered as the transducer. This concept implies that the sensor output remains stable even if the transducer is partially damaged because each transducer is composed of a large number of RNPs.

The RNPs transducer chip considered during the experimentation is composed of a quartz substrate with 8 square cells of 1mm^2 of nano-pillars arrays in it, as Figure 3 and 4 shows. Each cell of nano-pillars is considered as an RNPs transducer. Each nano-pillar is composed of 10 pairs of Bragg Reflectors ($\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{SiO}_2$) with a central cavity of 200nm of SiO_2 . The diameter of the pillars is close to 200nm and the height is approximately 2000nm . The lattice parameter among the Pillars forming the array is 500nm . In Figure 5 we show a microscope image of a nano-pillars array.

FIGURE 3. A chip with 8 RNPs transducers and its holder.

FIGURE 4. Magnified image with a microscope of a chip with 8 RNPs transducers illuminated from the back of the substrate.

FIGURE 5. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image of an RNPs array.

B. OPTICAL INTERROGATION SYSTEM

The setup considered during the experimental campaign is shown in Figures 6 and 7. In this setup, the RNPs transducer is completely immersed in the fluid being analyzed, which is inside a vessel. The liquid is in constant agitation by an Agimatic E-C magnetic stirrer (by J.P Selecta) under the vessel with a magnet inside the fluid. The RNPs transducer is illuminated from the back of the substrate through an SL1 Tungsten-Halogen lamp by StellarNet, with a spectral range of 350 to 2200nm. Note that RNPs transducers are passive devices, therefore, an external light source is needed to illuminate the transducer. The light reflected by the RNPs transducer is acquired by a CCD spectrometer HRS-VIS-005 by Migthex, with a bandwidth of 390 to 780nm.

FIGURE 6. Optical layout design of the interrogation platform.

FIGURE 7. Interrogation platform used during the experimentation.

A given RNPs transducer is connected to the acquisition system through a hand-made fiber optic probe composed of two multi-mode fiber optic cables, gathered in a ferrule aligned with the RNPs transducer. Note that only one of the 8 available RNPs transducers in the chip is used so as to simplify the setup. The two fiber optic cables have a core of $200\mu\text{m}$ and a numerical aperture of $0.22\mu\text{m}$, ending in a SubMiniature A (SMA) connector, where one of the fiber optic cables is connected to the light source and the other is connected to the spectrometer. As Figure 8 shows, a plastic

holder was created with Solidworks and fabricated with an Ultimaker 2 3D printer in PolyLactic Acid (PLA) to secure the alignment between the fiber optic probe and the RNPs transducer. Note that the RNPs transducer was cleaned with isopropanol and dust-less dried air before starting the experiments to avoid inaccuracies due to dirt.

FIGURE 8. Plastic holder designed to secure the alignment between the fiber optic probe and the RNPs transducer.

The interrogation set-up is controlled by a software developed by ourselves, which is composed of two parts: data acquisition and data processing. On the one hand, the acquisition program (coded in C++ under Visual Studio 2018) saves 60 responses per minute of a single RNPs transducer in text files, using the timestamp as a file identifier. This first program also allows configuring parameters of the spectrometer, such as acquisition time and calibration, as well as applying preprocessing algorithms to the signal, such as dark correction and filtering. In this regard, the authors considered during the experiments an acquisition time of 100ms , a number of wavelengths equalling 3648 (the number of points in a signal), dark correction, and filtering through a second order Savitzky Golay with a temporal window of 201 points. On the other hand, the data processing program (coded in MATLAB 2018a with the Statistical and Machine Learning Toolbox) considers the previously obtained data files to infer a property using both the WSRM approach and the PCA-based spectral analysis method.

C. AGRO-FOOD EXPERIMENT

The authors mimic an agro-food experimental study, where a fermentation process is emulated by measuring ethanol concentration over time in two matrices: DIW and WW. In both cases, the ethanol concentration is increased every ten minutes by $1\%vol.$, adding pure ethanol (Sigma-Aldrich $>99\%$) to the mixture in agitation. The data from these two experiments were obtained using the optical interrogation system previously discussed in Section III-B. This interrogation system was validated before starting the experiments. To this end, the system was used for getting some RNPs responses for several usual solvents as was described for the Figure 1 in Section I.

As for any dataset generation, we should identify conflicting samples, which could negatively affect the performance of the compared methods. In this regard, we detected transients during the addition of ethanol before the stabilization

FIGURE 9. RNP's transducer responses during the DIW-ethanol experiment, where the resonant mode zone is enlarged.

of the ethanol concentration. As a consequence, we removed a time interval of one minute before and one minute after the addition of ethanol. Outliers caused by vibrations and/or the presence of bubbles were also detected. Thus, outlier removal methods were applied based on the mean of the samples.

We include specific details of the datasets generated after removing transients and outliers:

- The DIW-ethanol experiment starts with an initial ethanol concentration of 1%vol., achieving a maximum ethanol concentration of 25%vol. The set includes 9549 responses of a single RNP's transducer, each one with 3648 points, labeled with ethanol concentration and time-stamp. Figure 9 shows a representative subset of the signals obtained.
- The WW-ethanol experiment starts with an initial ethanol concentration of 11%vol., achieving a maximum ethanol concentration of 27%vol. The set includes 7195 RNP's responses, each one with 3648 points, labeled with ethanol concentration and time-stamp. Figure 10 shows a representative subset of the signals obtained.

D. PERFORMANCE METRICS

This section describes some metrics used in ML to analyze the performance of regression algorithms, as well as metrics to analyze the performance of sensing systems.

On the one hand, focusing on metrics showing the predictive ability of a trained regression model, we have:

- Root-Square Mean Error (RMSE) is the square root of the average of squared errors (the differences between the values predicted by a model and the values observed). This formulation intensifies the significance of large errors and then is very sensitive to outliers. That is,

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}, \tag{8}$$

where y_i is the theoretical value and \hat{y}_i is the value predicted (the property of interest in the experiment) for

FIGURE 10. RNP's transducer responses during the WW-ethanol experiment, where the resonant mode zone is enlarged.

the i -th observation, with $i \in 1, \dots, m$. Note that the model will be better the smaller the RMSE, with a range of $[0, \infty]$.

- Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is the average of the absolute errors. This formulation is less sensitive than RMSE to outliers and is given by,

$$MAE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m |y_i - \hat{y}_i|. \tag{9}$$

Note that the model will be better the smaller the MAE, with a range of $[0, \infty]$.

- The coefficient of determination (R^2) measures how correlated is a group of observations to the prediction model, which is calculated as

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \bar{y})^2}, \tag{10}$$

where \bar{y} is the mean of the values predicted. Note that R^2 is in the range $[-1, 1]$, where the model will be correlated the closer R^2 to 1, the model will be inversely correlated the closer R^2 to -1 , and the model will not be correlated the closer R^2 to 0.

The previous metrics are calculated during the testing stage of the inference ML method to analyze. To ensure a robust evaluation stage, it is required to follow an adequate methodology, such as the usual k -fold cross-validation strategy. This technique is based on randomly partitioning a dataset in k sets $S = \{s_1, \dots, s_k\}$ of similar size. The method performs over k iterations. Thus, for the i -th iteration, the sets in $S - s_i$ are considered for training the model and the set s_i is used for testing purposes by calculating the previous metrics, with $i \in 1, \dots, k$. The metrics evaluating the inference ML method are calculated as the average for all iterations. In this paper, the authors consider a usual value of k equalling 9 to get a robust evaluation [26], [31].

On the other hand, focusing on metrics analyzing the performance of sensing models, we have:

- Sensitivity is defined as the quantification of the change in the transducer response due to a change of 1 unit in the property predicted. That means that for this experimental use case, sensitivity is defined as the change in the

space attribute produced by an increment of 1 % of the ethanol concentration in the analyzed matrix. Note that the space attribute will be given by the minimum of the resonant mode if the WSRM method is considered and the PCs if the case of the PCA-based method. Thus, sensitivity is calculated as the inverse of the slope for the ethanol inference equation in the inference stage, i.e., Equations (15) to (19) which will be introduced in the next section.

- Standard uncertainty characterizes the dispersion of the measurements which could be attributed to the measurand, where the lesser the uncertainty, the better the sensor [32], [33]. Following the recommendations by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), standard uncertainty mainly comes from two sources: the statistical uncertainty and the instrumental uncertainty. The statistical uncertainty is the lack of repeatably due to experimental factors, e.g., changes in the media temperature, and is calculated as

$$u_s = \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}, \tag{11}$$

where s is the average standard deviation for all samples in an experiment and n is the number of responses for each concentration of the solute. In this paper, s is calculated based on the reduced RNPs responses, meaning that the metric will be calculated based on the minimum of the resonant mode if the WSRM method is considered and the PCs in case of the PCA-based method. On the other hand, the instrumental uncertainty is produced by the inaccuracy of the spectrometer limited by its resolution and is calculated as

$$u_r = \frac{res}{\sqrt{12}}, \tag{12}$$

where res is the resolution of the spectrometer. Thus, standard uncertainty is calculating by combining both factors. However, we can obtain the standard expanded uncertainty by multiplying the standard uncertainty by a cover factor, that is

$$U = c \sqrt{u_s^2 + u_r^2}, \tag{13}$$

where c is the cover factor, which is a statistical safety factor to increase the confidence level. In this case, c equals 3, meaning a confidence level higher than 99%.

- Limit of Detection (LoD) defines the minimum concentration of analyte the sensor can distinguish with reasonable reliability in a sample without analyte, so the lower LoD, the better the sensor. Unlike sensitivity and uncertainty, LoD allows comparing directly different sensing models, being a standard evaluation metric reported in the literature [32]. Following IUPAC definition, LoD is calculated as the quotient between statistical uncertainty and sensitivity, that is

$$LoD = \frac{U}{Sensitivity}. \tag{14}$$

Note that experimental measurements are required to calculate LoD.

IV. RESULTS

This section discusses and compares the results obtained applying the WSRM and the PCA-based spectral analysis methods in the agro-food experiment. The section starts by describing the application of both methods to the experimental use case. Next, the results obtained are compared.

TABLE 1. Regression performance metrics for the DIW-ethanol experiment.

Regression method	PCA-based (with 2 PCs)			WSRM		
	RMSE	R ²	MAE	RMSE	R ²	MAE
Linear	0.2593	1.00	0.20836	1.1238	0.98	0.84445
Interactions Linear	0.19056	1.00	0.14497	1.1238	0.98	0.84445
Robust Linear	0.26176	1.00	0.20649	1.1590	0.97	0.83456
Stepwise Linear	0.19056	1.00	0.14497	1.1238	0.98	0.84445
Linear SVM	0.57028	0.99	0.51741	1.1253	0.98	0.84167

TABLE 2. Regression performance metrics for the DIW-ethanol experiment using the first PC.

Regression method	PCA-based (with 1 PC)		
	RMSE	R ²	MAE
Linear	0.4212	1.00	0.3527
Interactions Linear	0.4212	1.00	0.3527
Robust Linear	0.4227	1.00	0.3463
Stepwise Linear	0.4212	1.00	0.3527
Linear SVM	0.5988	0.99	0.5225

TABLE 3. Regression performance metrics for the WW-ethanol experiment.

Regression method	PCA-based			WSRM		
	RMSE	R ²	MAE	RMSE	R ²	MAE
Linear	0.14262	1.00	0.11267	1.0455	0.95	0.89928
Interactions Linear	0.14262	1.00	0.11267	1.0455	0.95	0.89928
Robust Linear	0.14262	1.00	0.11307	1.0461	0.95	0.90028
Stepwise Linear	0.14262	1.00	0.11267	1.0455	0.95	0.89928
Linear SVM	0.33653	1.00	0.30419	1.0666	0.95	0.92061

A. APPLICATION OF THE WSRM METHOD

Following the methodology exposed before for the WSRM method and the cross-validation strategy, all responses in $S - s_i$, the training set, for the DIW-ethanol experiment are reduced to a single point corresponding to the minimum resonant mode. On this basis, Figure 11(a) shows the property of interest in the experiment (the ethanol concentration) as a function of the minimum resonant mode. Analyzing this figure and due to the high linearity of the data, a linear model should be considered because otherwise, we could incur in an overfitting issue, which is a situation of concern in ML. Note that overfitting is incurred, when the model

(a) Resonant mode position (in wavelength shift) as a function of the ethanol concentration in the DIW-ethanol experiment.

(b) Resonant mode position (in wavelength shift) as a function of the ethanol concentration in the WW-ethanol experiment.

(c) First PC as a function of the ethanol concentration in the DIW-ethanol experiment.

(d) First PC as a function of the ethanol concentration in the WW-ethanol experiment.

FIGURE 11. Resonant mode position vs. first PC in DIW-ethanol and WW-ethanol experiments.

fits excessively the data, e.g., when noise is considered as true data. Thus, we propose to analyze the performance of WSRM while applying several usual linear methods: linear regression, interactions linear, robust linear regression, stepwise linear regression, and linear Support Vector Machine (SVM).

Table 1 compares the regression methods while applying the WSRM method to the reduced samples in s_i , the test set, for the DIW-ethanol dataset (see WSRM field in this table). Analyzing R^2 and RMSE metrics, the authors verify that robust linear regression and linear SVM are outperformed by the other methods. However, analyzing the MAE metric, it is reached that robust linear regression outperforms the other methods. This contradictory conclusion is due to the MAE metric is less sensitive to the magnitude of the error committed, while both RMSE and R^2 penalize this situation highly. Consequently, a method among linear regression, interactions linear, and stepwise linear regression should be chosen. The authors opted for selecting the method requiring lower computational complexity, i.e., linear regression. Thus, the ethanol concentration is inferred according to the equation based on linear regression given by

$$eth_{\{WSRM,DIW\}}(\%) = -3.3217 * 10^3 + 5.8123 * rmm, \quad (15)$$

where $rmm \in \mathbb{R}$ is the value of the minimum resonant mode for a sample.

Following with the WW-ethanol experiment and the same strategy as before, Figure 11(b) shows the ethanol

concentration as a function of the minimum resonant mode in $S - s_i$. Analyzing this figure, the same conclusion as before is reached, i.e., a regression model based on linear trends should be considered.

Table 3 compares the regression methods while applying the WSRM method to the reduced samples in s_i for the WW-ethanol dataset. Analyzing this table, the same conclusion is reached as for the DIW-ethanol experiment, i.e., the linear regression method should be selected. Thus, the ethanol concentration is inferred according to the equation based on linear regression given by

$$eth_{\{WSRM,WW\}}(\%) = -4.0035 * 10^3 + 6.9700 * rmm. \quad (16)$$

B. APPLICATION OF THE PCA-BASED SPECTRAL ANALYSIS METHOD

Following the methodology exposed before for the PCA-based method and the cross-validation strategy, all RNP's responses in $S - s_i$ for the DIW-ethanol experiment are considered for training PCA by assuming a CVP_{th} equalling 95%. As a result, two PCs were obtained explaining 87.7% and 11.8% of the variance, respectively. As the first PC explains a high variance, we could use this PC to understand how the data evolve in response to the increments of ethanol concentration. In this regard, Figure 11(c) shows the value of the first PC versus the ethanol concentration. Analyzing this figure, we check a linear correlation between the first PC

and the ethanol concentration. Therefore, a regression model based on linear trends should be considered.

Table 1 compares the regression methods while applying the PCA-based spectral analysis method with 2 PCs to the reduced samples in s_i for the DIW-ethanol dataset. Analyzing the R^2 metric, the Linear SVM regression method has worse performance than the other regression methods. The MAE metric indicates that interactions linear and stepwise linear regression techniques have a lesser error than the other regression techniques. Moreover, they also produce smaller errors than others due to having less RMSE value. Since both algorithms have the same metric values, the authors opted for selecting linear interactions because its computational complexity is lower than stepwise linear. Thus, the ethanol concentration is inferred according to the equation based on linear regression given by

$$eth_{\{PCA-B,DIW\}}(\%) = 12.6761 + 3.6954 * 10^{-4} * pc_1 - 8.3856 * 10^{-5} * pc_2 + 1.8245 * 10^{-9} * pc_1 * pc_2, \quad (17)$$

where pc_1 and pc_2 are the projections of an RNPs response in the space defined by PCA.

Additionally, as the first PC represents a high amount of variance (87.7%), the designers might simplify the system by means of incorporating only the first PC to the regression methods. Accordingly, Table 2 shows the regression performance metrics while applying the PCA-based spectral analysis method with only the first PC. Following the same criteria as before, the ethanol concentration is inferred using the equation based on linear regression given by

$$eth_{\{PCA-B_1PC,DIW\}}(\%) = 12.6761 - 3.7888 * 10^{-4} * pc_1. \quad (18)$$

Following with the WW-ethanol experiment, PCA is trained according to $S - s_i$ obtaining one PC explaining 96.8% of the variance. Figure 11(d) shows the value of the PC versus the ethanol concentration. Analyzing this figure, a linear correlation is observed, then a regression model based on linear trends should be considered.

Table 3 compares the regression methods while applying the PCA-based analysis method to the reduced samples in s_i for the WW-ethanol dataset. Analyzing the R^2 metric, all the methods obtain the same performance value. The MAE metric indicates that linear regression, interactions linear, and stepwise linear regression have a lesser error than other regression techniques. The RMSE metric shows that linear SVM is outperformed by the other regression algorithms. Consequently, an algorithm among linear regression, interactions linear, and stepwise linear regression should be selected. As before, the authors opted for selecting the algorithm with less computational complexity, which is linear regression. Thus, the ethanol concentration is

inferred using the equation based on linear regression given by

$$eth_{\{PCA-B,WW\}}(\%) = 18.8454 - 2.4628 * 10^{-4} * pc_1. \quad (19)$$

C. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE SPECTRAL ANALYSIS METHODS

Comparing both methods based on the regression performance metrics discussed before in Tables 1 to 3, the authors verify that the model obtained using the PCA-based spectral analysis method fits better the data than the WSRM method. This fact leads to an improvement in the system predicting the ethanol concentration. This improvement is also observed with the first PC in the linear fitting in Figures 11(a) to 11(d). Comparing Figures 11(a)-11(b) to 11(c)-11(d), the authors verify that the PCA-based spectral analysis method is less sensitive to the noise, which shifts the resonant mode when increasing the ethanol concentration.

The regression metrics analyzed in Tables 1 to 3 are useful to study how the model fits the data. However, they are not adequate to evaluate the sensing quality of the system. As an alternative, we calculate the sensitivity, uncertainty, and LoD metrics for WSRM and PCA-based spectral analysis methods in Table 4. As introduced before, sensitivity and uncertainty are not useful to compare different sensing systems, especially in this work where the sensing systems have different units (see abscissa axis in Figure 11). On the contrary, LoD is comparable and we verify that LoD is 140 and 137 times higher when the PCA-based approach is applied in DIW-ethanol and WW-ethanol experiments, respectively.

TABLE 4. Sensing performance analysis.

Experiment	Analysis method	Sensitivity	Expanded uncertainty	LoD
DIW-ethanol	WSRM	0.17 nm/[%]	0.05nm	1.261 [%]
	PCA-based (with 1 PC)	3427.24 a.u./[%]	105.34 a.u.	0.009 [%]
WW-ethanol	WSRM	0.14 nm/[%]	0.02 nm	1.509 [%]
	PCA-based	4060.42 a.u./[%]	151.26 a.u.	0.011 [%]

V. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a novel spectral sensing response analysis method for fluid characterization based on RNPs (Resonant Nano-Pillars) transducer signals, as an alternative to the conventional WSRM (Wavelength Shift of the Resonant Mode) method. To this end, the authors propose to simplify the RNPs (Resonant Nano-Pillars) signal through PCA (Principal Component Analysis), later inferring the feature of interest through regression algorithms from the ML (Machine Learning) field.

With the purpose of analyzing the performance of the proposal, the authors mimic an agro-food experiment, where they simulate a fermentation process by measuring the ethanol concentration over time in two matrices: DIW (Deionized Water) and WW (White Wine). The authors applied both the PCA (Principal Component Analysis) based spectral

analysis and the WSRM (Wavelength Shift of the Resonant Mode) methods to infer the ethanol concentration in both datasets. As a result, the authors verified experimentally that i) the ML (Machine Learning) model obtained using the PCA (Principal Component Analysis) based spectral analysis method fits better the data than the WSRM (Wavelength Shift of the Resonant Mode) method and ii) the sensing quality of the system, according to the LoD (Limit of Detection) metric, was increased up to 140 times. Thus, the authors conclude that the proposal can help to improve the ability of an RNPs (Resonant Nano-Pillars) transducer to infer chemical properties, especially when complex matrices, as the WW (White Wine) analyzed in this paper, are considered. Moreover, although this method has been demonstrated for RNPs (Resonant Nano-Pillars) transducers, most of the photonic transducers reported in the literature can benefit from the advantages of this method to improve the readout performance.

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